

INNOVATIVE PILOT LINES FOR SUSTAINABLE GRAPHENE-BASED FLEXIBLE AND STRUCTURAL ENERGY HARVESTING AND STORAGE DEVICES

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THE PROJECT

GRAPHERGIA unites European innovators to unlock the potential of laser-assisted graphene production to shape the future of smart, **self-charging textiles** and next-generation **Li-ion batteries**. Our mission is to seamlessly integrate energy harvesting into our clothing, making the charge-as-you-go lifestyle a reality for everyone. Weaving cutting-edge graphene tech into everyday life, GRAPHERGIA is set to power devices sustainably bridging the gap to the Internet of Things (IoT).

OBJECTIVES

- **Develop and implement innovative TENG power management circuits:** novel concepts and devices for power management circuits in flexible electronics to offer efficient interfacing between triboelectric nano-generator (TENG) and energy storage devices and fabrication of direct-current output TENGs.
- **Design and fabricate all-in-one TENG-based self-charging power textiles:** an integral approach for producing metal-free e-textiles on a large scale, serving as all-in-one, self-charging solutions, facilitating the transition to battery-less wearable electronics.
- **Devise and validate roll-to-roll digital-production processes:** a fully automated pilot line for laser-assisted deposition of conductive graphene coatings on textiles and high-performance Li-ion batteries (LIB) cell electrodes, complete with established process and quality control poised for industry 4.0 advancements.
- **Sustainability and life cycle assessment (LCA) studies:** formulate a commercialization plan grounded in standardized materials, processes, and prototypes with dependable functionalities. Leveraging established technologies in the 2D materials, smart clothing, and LIB cell markets, our aim is to mitigate negative social impacts by minimizing the use of critical resources and enhancing eco-efficiency.

METHODOLOGY

Standing on the consortium's current activities at TRL 3 or 4, GRAPHERGIA aims to explore pioneering concepts in 2D materials engineering and integration targeting TRL 5 or above. This involves establishing adaptable **pilot-scale methodologies** for the development of smart textiles and LIB cells, all grounded in the principles of **eco-design**. The laser-assisted process employed within GRAPHERGIA offers several distinct benefits, making it significantly relevant for industrial applications.

ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY

Zero waste and elimination of harmful chemicals in the manufacturing process.

COST-EFFECTIVENESS

Single-step process at ambient conditions; no requirements for special chambers or graphene post-treatment.

SCALABILITY

High-speed manufacturing; enabled by laser-powered in-situ graphene production and direct integration.

QUALITY

Our method results in graphene quality in harmony with the ISO graphene standards.

RESOURCEFULNESS

Precursor compounds (polymers, biomass-derived products) have been successfully transformed to high-quality graphene with minor irradiation modifications.

ADAPTABILITY

No graphene transfer to other substrates is required.

NTT TECHNICAL ACTIVITIES

PECVD will be used because this technology retains the fluorocarbon chemical compound functionality, the adhesion to most substrates and the mass manufacturing quality control. NTT will test the performances of the smart e-textiles towards achieving robust prototypes for long-term usability.

CONTACT US

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